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MODERN METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *This article describes how to use interactive methods to improve students' oral communication and, by using modern pedagogical and technological methods, and, by the way, introducing leading teaching styles, to teach younger generations, the system of easy communication in these languages can be fully developed.*

Keywords. *Curriculum, subject, method, innovation, vocabulary, style, traditional.*

The growing interest in many parts of the world in modern methods of teaching English raises the question of how this should be done - how the curriculum, subject, content and methodology should differ from the usual norms developed in the past. Much has been written about traditional English teaching, and until recently, the demand for information on modern methods of teaching English was limited. Nowadays, many books and articles have been written to draw attention to the issue. In planning the curriculum and methods, it was suggested that understanding the Learners and their needs, interests, abilities, likes, dislikes and level of development should take precedence over other considerations. By using modern pedagogical and technological methods, and by introducing advanced teaching styles, teaching the younger generations, it is possible to fully develop the spoken language system in these languages. And the possibilities of foreign partnerships help to develop it. [1]

The innovations and new teaching technologies that we know of give good results. Sometimes using the same styles in language teaching can reduce the student's interest in the language. We recommend using some types of teaching so as not to reduce interest in a foreign language. For example: 1. Dialogic speech - in this way, students creatively talk to each other. "Modern methods of teaching English put "Speaking in dialogues" in first place for developing speaking skills. These skills can be trained with the help of various textbooks, including fiction texts. Such dialogues make it possible to move away from the traditional transmission of texts and turn them into living English speech." Moreover, all the vocabulary is remembered much better. In dialogues, students train their fluency, reaction speed, acting skills and, of course, grammatical correctness.

2. The student himself reads the text and communicates the meaning. Reading is interactive. Reading stories, novels and other literary works written by famous Russian, English and American writers is very important in language learning. As an English teacher, you can apply various reading strategies, analyze literary elements, use various strategies to read unfamiliar words and expand vocabulary, prepare, systematize and present literary interpretations.

3. Listening comprehension - in this way, students can improve their speech skills. Listening is a receptive form of speech activity. Speech comprehension when listening is mainly based on auditory sensations. Perceiving, reproduce what we hear in the form of inner speech. Listening is impossible without the work of the speech motor analyzer. Of course, inner speech requires the ability to speak this language.

Understanding spoken language at the moment of understanding is accompanied by intellectual activity, including recognizing speech means and interpreting the content. [2, p. 10-12]

4. Learning English through watching films. Nowadays, teachers take into account the need of students to watch real film stories along with reading books, magazines and newspapers. After all, as is known, not only printed materials can serve as an excellent source of learning, but also songs and films play a key role in learning foreign languages.

5. The importance of teaching vocabulary. Vocabulary is one of the aspects of the language that will be taught in institutes. In addition to learning new vocabulary, the student must be able to use strategies to cope with unfamiliar vocabulary encountered in listening or reading text, to fill in the gaps in productive vocabulary in spoken and written speech, to use familiar vocabulary fluently and to learn new words. In isolation.

Learning vocabulary in itself is not endless. A rich vocabulary facilitates listening, speaking, reading and writing skills.

Discussion. According to the type of teaching in the traditional style, several aspects are distinguished, namely, such as speaking, analytical reading, reading at home, grammar practice, practical phonetics. As a result, 3-4 teachers teach students in different styles and as a result, the connection of aspects is not ensured. [3, p. 87-90]

Some students learn grammar well, but in speech they encounter difficulties in pronouncing words. On this path, we encounter some questions. This may be correct, but in the course all aspects of teaching in the new style are carried out in parallel. Theory is given, reinforced with various exercises, games, discussions in one class. We talked about groups that have achieved good results in the following methods.

1. The level of students' knowledge and assimilation capabilities are studied, and then tasks are given in this way.

2. The students' attention is attracted to the fullest extent, and no student is ever left without attention.

3. In the lesson, students speak mainly in a foreign language, the translation of incomprehensible words is not pronounced immediately, but they try to implement them with the help of facial expressions

4. Students are divided into small groups and use the following techniques: "work out discussions", "express your own opinion", "realize together".

5. Give students the opportunity to think freely and express their opinions, and their mistakes are not corrected immediately, but after the students speak, they are discussed together.

6. Various grammar, phonetic and other types of games are organized. Thus, roles are shared with students depending on their knowledge

7. Retell the text, pop pictures and watch short films and discuss them together, listen to the news on the topic and try to implement them. [4, p. 5-6]

In addition, there are some methods to improve learning a foreign language. The lessons are taught entirely in English based on all the experiences necessary for the lessons. That is, students begin to understand by reading, listening, practicing writing, improving their speech and others. Students become the focus of the lessons, not the teachers. The teacher only helps the student gain knowledge. Thus, there is an opportunity for self-study. When the lessons are non-traditional, the tasks are divided into a pair or a small group of students depending on their type, and then the students work in groups or individually. For example, at the beginning of the lesson, the teacher makes a plan and shares the news with the students. Each student participates in this plan and shares news with each other. As a result, there is a mutual exchange of knowledge, and all students become familiar with the topic. Some exercises are done in pairs or groups of students. For group work, students are given tasks such as: organizing debates, discussing a topic with role-playing, working with high technologies. For pair work, they are given dialogues, grammar materials, and reading. With these methods, we can make all students participate in the lesson, and the teacher can help each student according to his or her requirements.

Analysis and results. We wanted to say that the main thing in learning a language is to attract students, that is, they need motivation. It is necessary to keep students active during and after lessons. Teachers all over the world are always searching for how to successfully teach foreign languages to students.

There are many effective teaching methods. Among the main differences between traditional methods and modern ones is that modern teaching refers to "student-centered teaching", raising the

learning process to such a scale that it is not only useful but also interesting for students. Good doses of such activities as project work, dialogue development, speech skills development, group/pair work, whole-class activities, student motivation, various games, role-playing games and physical exercises become important in modern teaching. Today, teachers are faced with the fact that, like other craftsmen, foreign language teachers need both models and tools. In addition to basic theory, goals, and objectives—a vision or model of what is to be created—they must gain, through study, reflection, trial and error, and experience, the necessary experience in using the tools needed to succeed in their craft. [5, p. 109-111]

They must think seriously about how to raise their work to a higher level of usefulness and joy. Teachers who study and use modern methods of teaching English are those who care about their own value - to themselves, to their families, to society, to the world. And, most importantly, they care about their students - care enough to want to constantly improve their teaching for the sake of their students. Finally, these people are doers - practical achievers in their chosen profession. Therefore, we are confident that our work will be of great value and will help teachers who want to become modern and up-to-date professionals. Modern methods of teaching English can be both challenging and demanding for teachers and students; they can also be very stimulating and rewarding. The extent to which we can apply these approaches in our institution may depend on the readiness of our students, the skill of our teachers and their willingness to accept these Modern methods, and the availability of resources in our environment. Moreover, there is now a clear need to raise the standard of education at the highest institutional levels. I am a strong believer in the need to create a collaborative classroom environment, an intellectual and informational approach to learning, training students to generalize, to make deductive inferences, and to develop their ability to discuss and study individually. It is important to provide every opportunity to broaden and expand the range of activities throughout life. Good teaching strategies and methods include careful planning and balancing, different learning sequences with clear, achievable goals, so that students know what is expected of them. They also include project work (class magazines, group wall displays) involving students in joint decision about what to do themselves, collaboration, student self-assessment, role-play, group work, pair work, dialogues. All this will help students develop their ability to work more effectively. "Modern methods of teaching English put "Speaking in dialogues" in first place for developing speaking skills. These skills can be trained with the help of various textbooks, including fiction texts. Such dialogues make it possible to move away from traditional transmission of texts and turn them into living English speech." Moreover, all the vocabulary is remembered much better. train fluency, reaction speed, acting skills and, of course, grammatical correctness. Group and pair work have become so ingrained in our daily teaching routine that we can hardly pause to think before dividing the class to solve a specific communicative task. Group work has allowed the teacher to devote more time to the students' oral production, which may not have been a priority in foreign language classes before. Another important point is motivation. It is well known that motivation has a great influence on a student's ability to learn. Motivation can be divided into external and internal forms. Internal forms come from the students themselves, who want to learn for the sake of learning. The good news for teachers is that we can do a lot in the classroom to increase the level of external motivation. [6, p. 4-5] Circle games are very useful activities in which the whole class participates in a circle. Many games rework vocabulary and include an element of fun. Pair and small group work are in vogue at the moment. The communicative approach encourages teachers to use a lot of pair work and therefore to increase the "student talk time". I believe that in order to build group cohesion and for good group dynamics to prevail, there are times when the class needs to work together as a unit. Circle games are a good opportunity to build group cohesion. It is now widely recognized that individual students have different learning styles, strategies and preferences. It is also recognized that for lessons to be effective, there needs to be a change of pace and focus to keep students focused. For both of these reasons, it is important that teachers have as wide and flexible a repertoire as possible. [7, p. 3]

Conclusion. In conclusion, the key strategies for teaching English are probably to create a positive and collaborative working atmosphere and to provide a variety of work suitable for different levels.

I must say that it is almost impossible to use one method or approach exclusively for successful second language teaching. Lessons must be designed using effective teaching methods. In this way, we will achieve our teaching goals successfully.

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